

FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL COMPETENCIES AND CREATIVITY IN FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS.

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Abstract.

This paper discusses the aspect of the concept of “creative competence of a primary school teacher, the concept of pedagogical abilities, the conditions for the formation of pedagogical abilities.

Keywords: competence , professional activity , creativity , creativity , creative competence , primary school teachers

The transformations taking place over the past few decades in Uzbekistan could not but affect education.

At present, one of the important directions in the formation of professional competencies of primary school teachers is to increase readiness for the implementation of state educational standards. It is teachers who must ensure the solution of such an important task of an educational institution when introducing and improving the pedagogical process and increasing the developmental effect of educational work.

Competence is the result of education, which is expressed in a person's readiness to solve certain problems in professional and non-professional activities based on the use of internal and external resources.

The competence-based approach to the professional training of a future teacher is focused on the formation and development of a student-teacher's creative readiness and appropriate didactic readiness, reflects the modern understanding of the norms and values of a teacher's professional activity. However, the desire to follow the path of

creativity in their own pedagogical activity encounters a lack of experience in creative pedagogical work.

More important problem in today's school than the problem of professional development of beginners teachers. Who will help young teachers in her decision ? It would seem that there is nothing easier than to turn to pedagogical science for help and use its proven in practice, conclusions and recommendations. But what conclusions and recommendations of modern pedagogy can expect young teachers who are starting their independent ascent to impregnable pedagogical peaks? Novice teachers like air need practical

Technologies of their professional development and progressive development in the direction of comprehending the heights of pedagogical skill. Instead, modern pedagogy offers them Ever rests of learned literature with a description of how

be the perfect teacher and the perfect learning process. The authors of these books sincerely believe that they have successfully completed the most difficult part of the work. And the rest should be done by young teachers on their own. As a result of such scientific and methodological support each side remains in its own interests on opposite poles of the pedagogical globe. Why have the desired changes not occurred in solving this problem for many decades?

Here are some authoritative opinions on the matter.

Podlasy I.P.: Pedagogical theory is an abstraction. And its practical implementation is always high art. The conclusions of pedagogy are highly probable and uncertain. In many cases it only establishes the norm, but does not provide the achievement of this norm with scientific support.

Slastenin V.A. _ and others: "... Our pedagogical science is still seriously lagging behind life, weakly responding to the changes taking place in society, does not show social vigilance and courage in the analysis of contradictions and developing ways to solve urgent problems"

Rozanov V.V.: “Having a number of didactics, a number of methods, pedagogy as a theory of a certain craft, or art, we do not have”

Isn't this the landscape of our chronic stumbling, miscalculations and pedagogical mirages in the professional development of novice teachers. The causes of our pedagogical troubles are in a different plane.

One of the tasks of pedagogical education, focused on the formation and development of the professional competencies of the future teacher, is the revision of the professional worldview and the acquisition of new educational experience, creative behavior, and the development of creatively significant personal qualities. The solution to this problem will be the development of such an educational program that would contribute to the creation of a creatively developing educational space, saturated with innovative ideas and technologies, organized in such a way as to promote the creative self-development of a student teacher.

A characteristic feature of the program is the enrichment of the didactic component of the creatively developing educational space with pedagogical situations in which the algorithm for the creative transformation of the behavioral experience and pedagogical activity of the future teacher is laid down.

Another feature of the program for the formation and development of professional and creative competencies of a primary education teacher is the “personal-developing” approach (L.M. Mitina), the main components of which are:

- knowledge in the field of creative psychology and pedagogy;
- creative skills;
- creative readiness.

The assessment of the professional activity of an elementary school teacher is ambiguous, for example, it can be assessed from the standpoint of various approaches:

The teacher is a modern specialist in the field of education. When viewed from this point of view, the teacher's personality includes two components - competence. Primary school teacher - teacher and educator of children of primary school age. The

teacher is the bearer of professional pedagogical culture as an integrative personal professionally significant education, which includes five components presented in the table

Components of pedagogical culture	Characteristics of the teacher's activity
Communicative component	Openness for communication and cooperation with students in the classroom and outside of school hours
structural component	Organization of the activities of schoolchildren and their own professional activities
Perceptual Component	The ability to understand the emotional state and motives of the pupil's behavior, the ability to empathize (empathy)
Innovative Component	The need for innovation, for updating professional experience, pedagogical search
Reflective Component	Awareness of one's professional activity as the main sphere of one's personal self-determination, self-assessment of one's professional development

After analyzing the quality of the implementation of the function of managing the educational process by future primary school teachers, we can conclude that some successfully cope with this function and many of them switch to self-management (self-control) mode. Others experience significant difficulties:

- in combining pedagogical tasks and selecting relevant educational, upbringing and developing methods and technologies that correspond to them, managing these processes;

- in an attempt to overcome the constantly felt lack of personal time;

- in understanding the purpose of their professional activity, its compliance with personal needs and interests;
- in the development of ways with a mental state regulation during the working day, after it, ways of regulating the mental states of students;
- in independent and timely decision-making (in the choice of goal-oriented and unambiguous, situational or long-term priorities), etc.

It should be noted that the managerial function of the teacher is so important in understanding e e e by the teacher himself (which, we repeat, is not yet in reality at a sufficient level), that without this, the priority goal of his professional activity loses its meaning - organizing the life of the student team, organizing the educational activities of each child. The containment of some motives of activity and the activation of others (aiming at overcoming contradictions and difficulties) is the moment of controlling the will of the pupil, his emotional state. In addition, the teacher himself is in a situation of constant stress (a huge amount of volitional efforts), and therefore he must be able to remove it in a timely manner both in himself and in children (to manage the states of the muscular system of the body).

The ability to self-manage, for example, mental states and behavior, which allows you to optimally act in difficult pedagogical situations (simple situations need less control), in psychology is called the ability of a teacher to self-regulation.

A teacher working with a group of students must have a good idea of the formative role of the family and the dependence of this role on the value orientations of its members. Possession of such information makes it possible to foresee how relationships in the family can affect the personal development of the child, his character, and behavioral reactions. The interaction of the teacher with parents has a serious impact on the younger student during the period of adaptation. The interaction is also determined by the social requirements of society, which increasingly require the full cooperation of the teacher with the family. For the formation of cooperation between adults and children, it is important to represent the team as a single whole, as

a large family that unites and lives interestingly if the joint activities of teachers, parents, and children are organized.

Psychological-pedagogical, normative-legal and reflective competencies are general professional, i.e. necessary for all teachers.

Subject and methodological competencies belong to the category of special competencies, they ensure the fulfillment of specific professional duties that are characteristic of a primary school teacher and make it possible to distinguish him from other teachers. The listed competencies are closely interconnected, forming a complex structure, and their content represents the requirements for the professional activity of an elementary school teacher.

Table - The main professional pedagogical competencies of the future primary school teacher

Competencies	Characteristics of competencies
Personal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - activity in protecting the interests of students; - commitment to the profession; - ability to make decisions independently; - focus on goal setting and goal achievement ; - mental balance; - humanity; - versatility of personality; - pedagogical reflection; - pedagogical culture
Psychological and pedagogical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - knowledge: methodological, theoretical, methodical, technological; - skills: informational, organizational, communicative, pedagogical technique, applied; - subject competencies

subject- creative	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - independent comprehension and creative approach in solving pedagogical problems; - creation of situations conducive to the motivation of students; - encouraging students to be creative; - the use of non-traditional methods, methods and techniques in teaching; - carrying out experimental work; - research activities
methodical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - goal-setting and planning of pedagogical activity; - self-control; - self-regulation of moral-volitional and other mental states; - effective time management; - independent and timely decision-making; - designing, designing and implementing an effective educational process; - methods of covert control of students' minds

Thus, a professional as an integral person must have a set of significant professional and pedagogical qualities that allow him to most effectively implement the goals and objectives of his professional activity.

Being practice-oriented, the training of primary school teachers is complete. Thus, a graduate of a pedagogical college or higher education institution must carry out his professional functions at the level of a master.

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